

NEXT GENERATION SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES: DEVELOPMENT AND PROCESSING OF FURAN-FLAX BIOCOMPOSITES

E. L. Arnold* and B. M. Weager
NetComposites Ltd
4A Broom Business Park, Bridge Way, Chesterfield, S41 9QG, UK
elaine.arnold@netcomposites.com

H. E. Hoydonckx
TransFurans Chemicals bvba
Industriepark Leukaard 2, B-2440 Geel, Belgium
hans.hoydonckx@transfurans.be

B. Madsen
Materials Research Division, Risø National Laboratory for Sustainable Energy,
Technical University of Denmark
P.O. Box 49, Frederiksborgvej 399, DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark
boma@risoe.dtu.dk

ABSTRACT

The work presented in this paper was undertaken as part of BIOCOMP (2005-2008), a European collaborative project, which developed new classes of engineering composite materials from renewable resources. Comprising twenty five European SMEs and research organisations, this three and a half year project generated a wide range of new biocomposite materials, knowledge-based processes and demonstrator components.

This study focused on furan thermosetting bioresins, which are made from agricultural waste products such as sugar cane bagasse. Preliminary work included developing a two-part resin and catalyst furan system suitable for hand lay-up with glass fibres. The incorporation of flax fibres into the furan system required significant modifications to the resin chemistry. A high-performance, furan-flax prepreg system was developed, resulting in biocomposites with comparable mechanical properties to conventional glass fibre composites. A number of demonstrator parts were produced for comparison with components currently manufactured using conventional materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has recently become a key issue in the design and manufacture of products, due to dwindling oil reserves and increased environmental awareness. The use of natural fibre reinforced composites has seen a sharp increase, although these tend to be, firstly, short, randomly oriented fibres and, secondly, incorporated with synthetic polymers [1,2,3]. Although partly bio-based, the use of such materials has so far been restricted to low performance applications due to relatively poor mechanical properties. Considering the high specific stiffness of bast fibres such as hemp and flax

compared with glass, there is a strong argument technically [4], as well as environmentally, for the use of such materials in light weight composites.

Despite steps having been made to reduce the environmental impact of producing composite materials by replacing glass fibre with natural fibre, a collaborative study published by the Building Research Enterprise [5] found that the most damaging component to the environment in composites is in the synthesis of the resin/matrix. There is, therefore, a suggestion that alternative resins need to be used in order to reduce the environmental impact of composite production.

By using long, aligned natural fibres in conjunction with naturally derived resins, 100% bio-based composites with improved mechanical properties can be achieved and can potentially be employed for more structural purposes.

Furan bio-resin has been used extensively in the foundry industry for a number of years as a binder in sand moulds due to its excellent resistance to thermal and chemical attack. Derived from hemicellulose, which are typically found as waste products from the agricultural industries (typically sugar cane bagasse), these resins attracted interest for use in composite materials for high performance applications.

Figure 1: Schematic of processing route from hemicellulose to furan prepolymer, source TransFurans Chemicals

Work in this study began using glass fibre as reinforcement for the two-part furan resin system. This was then followed by substituting glass fibre for hemp and flax fibre. Due to the poor properties of these materials, considerable modifications were made to the resin to render it suitable for natural fibre. The resulting system was a natural fibre/furan prepreg.

Textile Choice

In this study, commercially available fabrics were used as reinforcements in the composite materials. Jute, hemp and flax fibres were all trialled in this study, flax having the best properties, as well as having the widest availability on the commercial level.

The majority of yarn spun using discontinuous fibres follows traditional spinning routes, by introducing a twist to the roving, friction between individual fibres holding the yarn together. The tensile strength of a yarn will increase linearly with increased levels of twist up to a critical point, beyond which, the fibre breaks, thereby steadily decreasing the properties of the yarn. By contrast, a yarn impregnated with resin shows a steady decrease tensile strength with increased levels of twist. This effect was investigated by Goutianos et al [6]. The introduction of a twist in a yarn causes a misalignment in the fibres, as well as limiting the impregnation of resin into the core of the yarn. These effects are both undesirable in composites, which will be demonstrated in this paper.

The weave style of the textiles used as composite reinforcements also bears a large influence on the resulting composite properties. The misalignment caused by yarns passing over and under each other, known as crimp, adds to the misalignment of individual fibres. The formability of the fabric is another consideration important to the choice of reinforcing material.

2. TWO-PART FURAN RESIN WITH GLASS FIBRE

Materials and Methods

Glass fibre was used as reinforcement for furan resin as an interim stage, before using natural fibre.

Laminates were made using a glass chopped strand mat (450gsm) hand laid with a two-part furan resin (Biorez 050905), mixed with a catalyst (up to 6% by weight) supplied by Transfurans Chemicals (TFC). A vacuum was applied to the mould in order to restrict the amount the laminates shrunk during curing and to evacuate any additional water produced during curing. The cure cycle ran from 150 minutes at 20°C, 45 minutes at 50°C and 45 minutes at 80°C. The plaques were 2mm thick and tested in tension and flexure according to ISO 527-4 and ISO 14125 respectively.

A reference material was also made using glass fibre and unsaturated polyester, namely Crystic 489PA from Scott Bader with 2 wt% MEKP catalyst. Laminates were approximately 44% fibre by weight.

Glass/furan laminates were mechanically tested at ambient temperature and at a range of different temperatures.

Results and Discussion

Mechanical tests performed on both glass/furan and glass/polyester laminates showed comparable properties and in the case of tensile modulus, glass/furan outperforming

the reference material. However, flexural strength and modulus were both well below the GRP values. Table 1 shows some mechanical properties of these materials.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of glass/furan and glass/polyester laminates

Material	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
Glass/polyester (reference material)	7.1	123	6.2	214
Glass/furan	7.7	103	4.7	110

Figure 2: Tensile strength of glass chopped strand mat/furan as a function of temperature. Laminates were all hand laid.

Figure 3: Tensile modulus of glass chopped strand mat/furan as a function of temperature.

Little reduction in tensile modulus and strength was seen in laminates tested in temperatures up to 200°C. Easby et al [7] reports a reduction in tensile strength in the region of 100MPa in polyester and phenolic/glass reinforced pultruded composites

tested in a similar range of temperatures. By contrast, the glass/furan showed a reduction of only 30MPa.

3. TWO-PART FURAN RESIN WITH NATURAL FIBRE

Materials and Methods

Laminates were then produced by vacuum infusing glass, flax and hemp mats with a low viscosity furan resin (Biorez 060214-U-I (222cps)). The same was done using polyester resin from Scott Bader, Crystic 702PA, for reference. The hemp used here was supplied by BAFA, Germany in the form of a non-woven mat (740gsm) and the non-woven flax mat was from Ekotex, Poland (570gsm). The laminates were then tested in three-point flexure according to ISO 14125.

Results and Discussion

Figure 4 shows the flexural modulus of the materials tested. In all cases, poor results were seen in the laminates using furan resin compared with the reference panels using polyester resin.

Figure 4: Flexural modulus of glass, hemp and flax mat reinforced furan and polyester. Laminates were all vacuum infused with fibre volume fractions in the region of 23%.

The effect of acidic conditions on hemp fibre was studied by Thygesen et al. 2007 [8] and indicates that the action of acids can cause hydrolysis in cellulose chains and other binding materials, thereby degrading the fibre bundle mechanical properties. Figure 5 shows the tensile strength of hemp fibre bundles as a function of pH level, the effects of acid clearly causing a reduction in strength. It was therefore evident that the 2 part furan resin was unsuitable for use with hemp and flax fibre due to the acidic catalyst used to cure it.

Figure 5: Tensile strength of hemp fibre bundles soaked in water solutions with various pH levels (*figure is from Thygesen et al. 2007 [8]*)

4. MODIFIED FURAN WITH NATURAL FIBRE

Materials and Methods

Significant alterations to the 2-part resin system were made in order to render it suitable for natural fibre. A pH neutral (pH 4-5) version using the trade name Furo-lite was then developed for this purpose. Due to the high viscosity of this resin, an alternative route to hand lay-up or vacuum infusion for impregnating the natural fibres was required. By diluting the resin in a solvent, such as water, the viscosity of the solution was reduced sufficiently for the textiles to be fully wetted out. The solvent was then driven off by heating, leaving fabrics impregnated with up to 60% by weight of furan resin.

As well as developing natural fibre furan prepregs, some initial trials were run using glass and carbon fibre as reinforcements.

In this study, 3 fabric styles were trialled (Figure 6):

1. Loosely woven plain weave flax fabric with highly twisted yarn (170gsm)
2. Tightly woven plain weave flax fabric with highly twisted yarn (106gsm)
3. Unidirectional stitched flax fabric with loosely twisted yarn (230gsm) (to enable a direct comparison, this fabric was laid up as a biaxial laminate)

Figure 6: Fabric styles 1, 2, and 3 respectively

Laminates using natural fibre prepreg were made by vacuum consolidating the materials at 150°C for 15 minutes. Laminates were approximately 40% fibre by volume.

Results and Discussion

Once a pH neutral resin was developed, trials were run using the prepreg system with the 3 different flax fabrics, the results shown in Figure 7. Clearly yarn twist and crimp have a significant effect on the resultant composite properties.

Figure 7: Flexural modulus of flax/furan prepreg fabrics. Laminate fibre weight fractions were estimated to be 51%, 59% and 44% respectively

A variety of processing trials were conducted to improve the surface finish of the furan-flax laminates and good results were achieved, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Surface finish of a) initial furan-flax prepreg laminates and b) improved furan-flax laminates

5. MODIFIED FURAN WITH GLASS AND CARBON FIBRES

The results of some flexural tests performed on glass and carbon reinforced furan are shown in Table 2. Interestingly, flax outperformed glass in terms of flexural modulus and had similar showed similar strengths.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of furan prepreg with various reinforcements.

Material	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Fibre Content (Vol)
Flax UD stitched fabric/furan (biaxial laminate)	9.6	99.4	41%
Glass plain weave fabric /furan	9.0	104.6	47%
Carbon fibre twill weave/furan	26.2	364.7	39%

6. CASE STUDY PARTS

Some shaped mouldings were manufactured as part of the BIOCOMP project. These included external automotive panels, bathroom flooring and complex shaped mouldings.

Figure 9: Case study shaped mouldings: a) glass/furan external vehicle panel, b) flax/furan automotive bracket and c) flax/furan bathroom flooring sandwich panel

The bathroom flooring panel used a sandwich structure containing 4mm thick flax/furan prepreg skins and a 20mm thick balsa wood core. This was tested under flexure at MERL, UK and was found to have high stiffness well within the requirements of the reference material, a sandwich particle board. The force/extension graph in Figure 10 shows the panels failing in a brittle manner. The primary mode of failure was delamination of the composite skins from the balsa wood cores. A widely published concern [9] in industry surrounding the use of natural fibre composites is that of variability. Figure 10. Shows a high element of reproducibility in terms of composite stiffness, which could be attributed to good fibre wet-out throughout the composite parts.

Figure 10: Force/deflection graph test results of flax/furan sandwich panel tested under flexure (*from MERL, UK*)

7. CONCLUSIONS

Glass/furan laminates performed well at high temperature and had properties comparable to glass reinforced polyester. Stiffness's similar to the reference synthetic material were achieved with the prepreg system developed for natural fibre/furan. Process developments enabled better surface finishes to be achieved. The case study components moulded as part of the BIOCOMP project demonstrated the abilities of the developed furan based materials to form complex shapes as well as to assess the feasibility of using these materials in semi structural applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study summarises much of the work undertaken as part of the BIOCOMP project, an integrated collaborative research project, supported by the European Commission through the 6th framework programme (Project No.NMP2-CT-2005-515769) under the Contract No. 515769. The support of all of the partners is gratefully acknowledged, in particular, MERL.

REFERENCES

1. T. M. Gowda, A.C. B. Naidu, R. Chhaya. *Some Mechanical Properties of Untreated Jute Fibre-reinforced Polyester Composites*. Composites Part A 30: 277- 284 (1999)
2. A. C. N. Singleton, C. A. Baillie, P. W. R. Beaumont, T. Peijs. *On the Mechanical Properties, Deformation and Fracture of a Natural Fibre/recycled Polymer Composite*. Composites: Part B 34; 519-526 (2003)
3. H.Y. Sastra, J.P. Siregar, S.M. Sapuan, Z. Ledman, M.M Hamdan: *Flexural Properties of Arenga Pinnata Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites*. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 21-24 (2005) ISSN 1546-9239
4. B. Madsen, A. Thygesen, H. Lilholt: *Plant fibre composites – porosity and stiffness*. *Composites Science and Technology* 69; 1057-1069 (2009).
5. BRE & NetComposites, *Green Guide to Composites*, BRE Bookshop (2004)
6. S. Goutianos, T. Peijs, B. Nystrom, M. Skrifvars: *Development of flax fibre based textile reinforcement for composite applications*. *Applied Composite Materials* 13; 199-215 (2006).
7. R.C. Easby, S.Feih, C. Konstantis, G. LaDelfa, V. Urso Miano, A. Elmughrabi, A.P Mouritz, A. G. Gibson: *Failure Model for Phenolic and Polyester Pultrusions Under Load in Fire*. *Plastics, Rubber and Composites* (2007) vol 36 no 9 379S.
8. A. Thygesen, B. Madsen, A.B. Thomsen, H. Lilholt: *Effect of acidic conditions on interface and strength of cellulose fibres*. In: *Proceedings of the 23rd Risø International Symposium on Materials Science*, Risø, Denmark, September 2007.
9. F Le Digabel, L. Avérous: *Effects of Lignin Content on the Properties of Lignocellulose-based Biocomposites*. *Carbohydrate Polymers* (22-04-2006)